

POLIRURAL

MAZOWIECKIE

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Main structure (feel free to expand)

1. Lessons learned
2. Main results achieved
3. Action Plan alignment and adoption
4. Pilot case study
5. Technical tools
6. Foresight tools (guides)

Information you provide will be added to the exploitation plan in response to reviewers' comments.

The study area: Mazowieckie

Mazowieckie Pilot Area

5,324,519 inhabitants, accounting for 13.7% of Poland's population, 35.7% of total population in the region live in rural areas and this number is growing!

Zielone Sąsiedztwo

Special Focus (case study area) consists of the 3 communes with 45 thousand inhabitants, located in the central part of the Mazowieckie region, in close proximity to the capital city, NGOs, local administration, citizens, entrepreneurs, civic society, education, researchers, aged 28-75.

Lessons

- Name lessons you have learned by working on your foresight pilot?
 - Time consuming with troubles: No good response from the regional administration (better at national level). Partly resolved by participation in public consultations and personal contacts.
 - There is a growing awareness in our region of the risks associated with global challenges, climate, demographics and renewed crises.
 - As a recommendation from the whole process we point out the need for personal contacts, in our case online did not work well. Personal participation obliges you to be active.

VS

Rural attractiveness and the vision

To go beyond the existing approaches and develop new, effective techniques to promote rural areas as a **place of living and working for newcomers, in the context of strong impact produced by the agglomeration of rural areas, as well as changing patterns in food consumption** (demand), health awareness and lifestyles

Expected outputs include **new services for local communities, better access to local food, improved serviced for better quality of life and better local social and technical infrastructure.**

Demographic shift, climate change as well as poverty and social inequalities are the most important challenges for rural areas in Mazowieckie. The diversity of rural areas is considered as a developmental challenge that must be tackled by area-tailored policies and by the cooperation of all the stakeholders. This also include **climate smart policy, capacity building for knowledge transfer and new businesses for high-quality job creation leading to better quality of life in rural areas.**

What do you consider to be the most significant results of your pilot?

- The multi-stakeholder collaboration. The core group was expanded with new members, new thoughts - this was necessitated by the PoliRural KPI, it helped the local community to look for new, active discussion group members.
- New knowledge about our region, thanks to deep dives and drivers analysis. The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change helped to start the exchange of ideas for future. SEMEX and Deep Dives 😊

Regional drivers

- Promote **job creation** with adequate pay and with a view to **supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, eco-firms and sustainable business** (circular economy).
- Have **sustainable settlements**, regions and landscape in the context of climate change.
- Improve quality of public services.
- Increase the number of sufficiently lively **communities and citizen-driven local activities** and **promote local organizations**, regional specialties, crafts, traditions
- Improve the **quality of health care services**
- Improve the **transport service** both within the territory and from the territory to urban areas, with particular attention to transport to health services.

DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF THE MAZOWIECKIE VOIVODESHIP 2030+

Action Plan

Alignment with LTV4RA: Please explain how planned actions will make your region

- Stronger – new business models responding to challenges and support to administration
- Connected – digitization issues
- Resilient – local assets promoted
- Prosperous – economic measures (businesses)

To be successful Action Plan must be adopted by key policy stakeholders. How do you intend to facilitate adoption and how would successful adoption look like? Please give examples

- Meetings with policy makers under public consultation proces for new strategic documents, round tables, responding to consultations, lobbying
- Successful adoption local strategy based on pilot results, introduction of measures recommended in the Action Plan, more funding allocated to proposed measures is expected in next programming period (measers in line with project results).

Tools (tech)

How do you intend to use these tools after the project?

- Semex: YES - text mining – very useful tool, need to be updated to be in use.. High interest of LAGs and local policy makers 😊
- Rural Attractiveness Explorer: YES, Good tool for seeking for policy options 😊
- Digital Innovation Hub: maybe, business development
- Atlas of Best Practices: to promote good ideas and practises

Tools (guides)

Which of the following do you intend to use after the project, and how?

- Guide to Deep Dives (Covid) – Very useful, and we use it for crisis now.
- Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform) - no
- Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal) – yes, help to organise the work and GD is ongoing
- The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change – yes!!
- D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology – yes
- Regional Action Plan – yes!